

Activity Follow-Up

After completing the activity (experiment using the LucidChart GPT tool), students must fill out a feedback form, which will address the following aspects: precision, clarity and comparison.

* Indicates a mandatory question

1. 1. Using Generative AI to generate UML diagrams increases productivity in software projects. *

Mark just one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Disc Totally agree

2. 2. The tool allows you to create UML diagrams faster than using manual methods. *

Mark just one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Disc Totally agree

3. 3. The activity UML diagrams generated by the tool are correct in terms of denotation and syntax *

Mark just one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Disc Totally agree

4. 4. The representations of software elements (such as activity, transition, and decision) are accurate and correct in the diagrams generated by the tool. *

Mark just one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Disc Totally agree

5. 5. The generated UML diagrams are complete and do not omit important information about the use case.

Mark just one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Disc Totally agree

6. 6. The diagram generated by the Lucid GPT tool is easy to understand and follows the standard conventions of UML. *

Mark just one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Disc Totally agree

7. 7. I am satisfied with the quality of the UML diagrams generated by the tool.

Mark just one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Disc Totally agree

- 8. I would recommend using Lucid GPT to other developers who need to generate UML diagrams.

Mark just one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Disc Totally agree

- 9. 9. In your opinion, is the manual diagram more, less, or equally complete and accurate compared to the diagram generated by Lucid GPT?.

Mark just one oval.

More comprehensive and accurate than the one generated by the tool

Less comprehensive and accurate than the one generated by the tool

As accurate and comprehensive as the one generated by the tool

- 10. Could you describe your experience considering the *difficulties* and *opportunities* in creating the manual diagram and the automatically generated one. *

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